

segregant analysis. TGMS line SA2, selected from mutagenified populations, was nonallelic to other sources of TGMS genes and was designated as tms4. TGMS and fertile bulks were made from the F₂ population of the cross SA2 (TGMS)/N22 (fertile). Seventy-five operon primers were used to examine polymorphism in SA2, N22,

and bulks. Seventeen polymorphic products were specific to the fertile parent N22 and 19 were specific to the TGMS parent SA2. Of these, the 0.7-kb amplicon of OPA12 and 1.9-kb amplicon of OPS1 were specific to the TGMS trait.

TGMS line ID24 was allelic to Norin PL 12 (tms2) and was nonallelic to SA2.

Earlier studies on tagging the Chinese TGMS source reported that the 1.2-kb amplicon was closely linked. A bulked segregant analysis of the F₂ of the cross ID24/N22 revealed that a 1.2-kb amplicon of OPB19 was specific to TGMS. Further studies related to mapping are in progress. ■

Breeding methods

Heterosis over environments in crosses involving indica and tropical japonica rice cultivars

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The discovery of wide compatibility genes in rice recently shifted the emphasis on enhancing heterosis from intervarietal hybrids to intersubspecific hybrids. We therefore studied the nature and magnitude of heterosis in inter- and intrasubspecific crosses involving improved tropical japonica (J) parents (BSI 10 [P1], BSI 16 [P2], B4116 [P3], and B4122 [P4]) and indica (I) parents (Govind [P5], Manhar [P6], Pant Dhan 4 [P7], Sarjoo 52 [P8], Pant Dhan 12 [P9], and Narendra 359 [P10]). We evaluated all 45 hybrids and parents in a randomized complete block design under environments with

optimum sowing and high fertility (E1), optimum sowing and optimum fertility (E2), and late sowing and high fertility (E3). We studied 10 agronomic traits, including harvest index and grain yield, for heterosis, hetero-beltiosis, and standard heterosis using Pant Dhan 4 as the standard variety.

Analysis of variance indicated a large variation among hybrids and parents. Moderate to high heterosis for yield and agronomic traits across environments was recorded. Trends in the magnitude of heterosis were $I/J > I/I > J/J$ for grain yield and plant height and $I/J > J/J > I/I$ for days to flowering. Standard heterosis for grain yield percentage in the respective E1, E2, and E3 environments ranged from -64.5 to 146.1, -70.4 to 82.2, and -67.2 to 63.8. E1 (optimum sowing and high fertility) gave a better response for heterosis expression.

Higher heterosis in grain yield accompanied heterosis in panicle number, total dry matter and/or

spikelet number, and grain number panicle⁻¹. Almost 95% of the hybrids recorded negative heterosis for flowering and some were earlier by 11-27 d across environments. Hybrids P3/P8 in E1, P4/P6 in E2, and P1/P5 in E3 recorded 19.1, 20.1 and 20.4% standard heterosis for earliness and 146.1, 66.8, and 60.2% for grain yield, respectively. Standard heterosis for height was 2.0-13.7% across environments. Both parents having *Sd1* genes caused F₁ height to increase only slightly. Promising hybrids for direct exploitation were P3/P8, P1/P9, and P1/P10 in E1; P4/P7, P4/P6, and P4/P10 in E2; P4/P7, P7/P9, and P7/P8 in E3; and P3/P8, P4/P7, and P4/P10 over environments. These hybrids showed good prospects for increasing potential yields and per-day productivity in the subtropics. Studies are in progress to improve parents for the thermosensitive genic male sterility trait and resistance against biotic stresses. ■

Plant regeneration from protoplasts of wild rice, *Oryza meyeriana* Bail.

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Oryza meyeriana is a wild rice species distributed in southern China and Southeast Asia. An accession found in China's Yunan Province has a strong resistance to bacterial leaf blight. It is

difficult, however, to transfer the disease resistance character of *O. meyeriana* to cultivated rice (*O. sativa*) by sexual hybridization because of sexual incompatibility between the two species.

Plant regeneration from protoplasts is important for rice breeding and is a prerequisite for genetic manipulation via somatic hybridization. Progress has been made in protoplast culture and regeneration of cultivated rice and other *Oryza* species. Plants have been recovered from cryopreserved calli in

O. meyeriana. Here, we report on successful plant regeneration from protoplasts of this wild rice.

The immature panicles in the stamen and pistil differentiation stage were taken from cryopreserved callus-regenerated plants and used as explants. Calli were induced on N6 medium containing 2 mg L⁻¹ 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, 45 g L⁻¹ sucrose, and 5 g L⁻¹ agar at pH 5.8. Pale yellow primary calli with a dry appearance were transferred to liquid AA2 medium. Fine dispersed calli were